

The Role of Experiential Marketing, Social Media Marketing and Brand Trust in Increasing Repurchase Intention

Lena Ellitan

Faculty of Business Widya Mandala Catholic University Surabaya, Indonesia
lena@ukwms.ac.id

Abstract

As the internet and digital technology advances, everything becomes limitless. Many claim that the industrial revolution era had an impact on several elements of society, including the economy. In order for the organization's desires and goals to be achieved and developed, as well as to contain competition, businesses must decide on new marketing strategies that are in line with the evolution of the times. The exchange of information in the form of marketing, sales, and customer support is one example of how internet use is still growing. Additionally, businesses can use the internet to strengthen their brands, defend their products, and build production and marketing plans. In the 21st century, several aspects of customer behavior, including perception, information processing, information sharing, views, attitudes, purchases, and follow-up behavior, have been influenced by social media. With the availability of web-based entertainment, companies can engage with their customers and receive feedback from them, and consumers can communicate with other consumers and share information about products and companies. Brand trust and intention to repurchase certain company products influence. To provide deals, agreements and associations with their buyers, many brands are now turning to online entertainment. Information and opinions can be easily announced using communication platforms. Buyer's trust in a brand (brand trust) according to Ngabiso et al (2021) is a brand limit that is trusted by customers when an item or administration can overcome problems that occur with the buyer's brand both in terms of certainty and focus on the buyer's needs, then that is seen by the company can trust and be responsible for customer needs and welfare. This article discusses the role of Experiential Marketing, Social Media Marketing, and Brand Trust in increasing Repurchase Intention. This article can be used as a reference for other research that has similar variables to this research, namely experiential marketing, social media marketing, repurchase retention, and brand trust. The author hopes that this research can further assess the variables of experiential marketing, social media marketing, and brand trust as factors that can damage repurchase interest.

Keywords: *experiential marketing, social media marketing, repurchase intention, brand trust.*

Introduction

The 4th industrial revolution is now underway, where technology has been assimilated into everyday life. As the internet and digital technology advances, everything becomes limitless. Many claim that the industrial revolution era had an impact on several elements of society, including the economy. Even though this period provides benefits, many people also view it negatively. The Internet of Things (IoT),

Big Data, Artificial Intelligence (AI), and Additive Manufacturing have all entered this revolution. Examples can be found all over the world, including Indonesia.

The changes brought by the fourth industrial revolution have increased competition in the Indonesian business sector as businesses continue to gain market share and new clients. For the sake of sustainability and organizational goals to achieve and develop, as well as outperform the competition, businesses must decide on new marketing strategies that are in line with the evolution of the times. The exchange of information in the form of marketing, sales, and customer support is one example of how internet use is still growing. Additionally, businesses can use the internet to strengthen their brands, defend their products, and build production and marketing plans.

People in Indonesia have felt the impact of advances in information technology through the use of platforms and devices. In Indonesia, there will be 210 million internet users in 2022. In Indonesia, there were 175 million internet users before the pandemic. In other words, the number of people using the internet rose by 35 million during the pandemic. According to the AAJI report, 77.02% of people had access to the internet at that time. For comparison, in 2018 the level of internet access was still 64.8% and in 2019-2020 it was around 73.7%.

Every year, the number of Indonesians who use social media continues to increase. According to the We Are Social report, the number of active social media users in Indonesia increased from 170 million in January 2021 to 191 million in January 2022 or 12.35%. WhatsApp is the application most widely used by Indonesian people. This figure reached 88.7% after Instagram which reached 84.8% and Facebook with a percentage of 81.3%. Meanwhile, 63.1% and 62.8% are Telegram and TikTok users. Companies use social media to promote their brands and get customers to buy from them again, due to the large number of social media users in Indonesia. Customers are also given the opportunity to interact directly with businesses through social media marketing. Social media marketing can also see how customers respond to the offer. Samsung is interested in utilizing social media as a means of promotion and communication with customers because of the close relationship between social media and consumer interest in making repeat purchases.

In the 21st century, several aspects of customer behavior, including perception, information processing, information sharing, views, attitudes, purchases, and follow-up behavior, have been influenced by social media. With the availability of web-based entertainment, companies can engage with their customers and receive feedback from them, and consumers can communicate with other consumers and share information about products and companies. According to a survey conducted in 2019 by content management service website HootSuite, revealed that there are 130 million mobile social media users in Indonesia, out of a total population of 268.2 million, which shows the growth of Instagram in the country. 80% of Indonesians, or more than 100 million people, are Instagram users. Indonesia ranks third on the list of countries that experience the most incidents of internet fraud, according to the findings of a 2016 examination conducted by Kaspersky Lab. As an illustration of fraud, Samsung Indonesia distributed free smartphones via WhatsApp..

Brand trust and intent to repurchase a particular company's products are affected. To provide correspondence, deals and associations with their buyers, many brands are now turning to online entertainment. Information and opinions can be easily shared using this communication platform. Web-based entertainment is seen as truer to buyers

because it conveys the brand. An important consideration to expand repurchase interest is to make buyers recall a brand again with the help of special media through online entertainment. Buyer trust in a brand (brand trust) according to Ngabiso et al (2021) is the limit of a brand that is trusted by customers when an item or administration can overcome problems that occur with the brand both in terms of buyer certainty and focusing on the buyer's needs, then it is seen that the company trustworthy and responsible for customer needs and welfare. This article discusses the role of Experiential Marketing, Social Media Marketing and Brand Trust in Repurchase Intention

Experiential Marketing

A marketing method called experiential marketing aims to provide customers with more than just facts about goods or services. Experiential marketing is an effort that focuses on analyzing customers as emotional and selfish humans who utilize consumption as a method to create meaningful experiences, according to Skandalis et al (2019). Meanwhile, experiential marketing is defined by Andriani and Fatimah (2018) as adding value to a good or service by influencing consumers' feelings when using the good or service.

Kustini in the journal Fahmi (2019) also said that something that is not much different is that experiential marketing is the practice of marketing products or services through positive experiences and emotional stimulation. From the definition above, it can be concluded that experiential marketing is a way that must be understood by companies in approaching and retaining consumers, from the experience gained and through products or services produced by the company by adding positive things and a sense of impression for consumers when carrying out the process of purchasing products or services, services, as well as presenting something unique and having characteristics that other products do not have.

According to Priansa (2017) experiential marketing includes five dimensions, namely as follows:

- a) Sense is an important and obvious part of a brand that is captured by the five human senses, including sight, sound, smell, taste and contact. The purpose of sense is to produce sensory experiences through touch, taste, smell, and sound. By attracting customers and providing positive value to products or services, sense can also be used as a competitive advantage for businesses and products.
- b) Feel, namely from a moderate mood to very strong sentiments of joy and pride, feelings and emotions are used to influence events. The purpose of feel is to attract consumers' attention and emotions by creating an experience of positive mood and soul that can evoke happiness or sadness. The way feel works is by having a strong understanding of certain emotional stimuli that can move emotions and the willingness of consumers to take part in views and empathy.
- c) Think, namely encouraging someone to think innovatively and critically which has the potential to significantly increase the evaluation of company products. Think aims to create cognition by appealing to consumer intellectuals and solving problems that involve consumers creatively. The target of think is to bring consumers to think in a centered and different way through surprise, collaboration

and provocation.

d) Act is a person's long-term effort to develop consumer experiences connected to their physical body, behavioral habits, and lifestyle based on contact with other people. Act has a target, namely improving consumer experience through physical experiences and real behavioral patterns in doing something.

e) Relate, namely the relationship experienced by consumers, whether with the company or with the community of people who use the company's products or services. Relate contains aspects of sense, feel, think, and act. But relate develops quickly through the consumer's personal abilities and feelings, thereby connecting the consumer's personality with something outside themselves. Relate aims to increase individuals' willingness to improve themselves. Companies interact with consumers through a wider social system.

Social Media Marketing

Social media marketing is a type of digital marketing that utilizes websites and social media to advertise products or services for businesses. This gives marketers an incredible opportunity to connect with customers in social groups and forge more intimate bonds with them. With social media marketing, it is easier for manufacturers or company owners to communicate with clients or customers online. Additionally, there are few costs involved and no time limits as long as they have access to the internet. Social media marketing according to Gunelius in the journal Mileva and Dh (2018) is all direct and indirect marketing that is used to increase awareness, recognize, remember and take action on using social media, such as managing blogs, writing ideas, social media, social bookmarks, providing information, companies, businesses, goods, and individuals can communicate. According to Mileva and Fauzi (2018), social media marketing is a method involved in empowering individuals to advertise their sites, works and products through friendly channels on the web and convey it using a much larger local area that has greater opportunities for promotion rather than through regular advertising channels.

According to Nunik et al (2019), social media marketing is an interactive marketing communication activity between businesses and customers, and vice versa, which helps these businesses generate sales of their goods and services. According to the definition given above, the practice of encouraging individuals to market their websites, products or consumer services through online social media channels and to communicate with each other is known as social media marketing. It taps into a much larger community with more opportunities for marketing than traditional advertising channels.

According to Afifah (2016), social media marketing has several indicators, namely as follows:

1. Online Communities, namely a business must create a community to offer its products to that community and encourage customer loyalty. Local area souls to build resilience, support conversations, and contribute data that is helpful in the turn of events and business progress.
2. Interaction, namely the company must engage with customers by responding to their comments, direct messages and broadcasts to make it easier for customers to obtain information from the business. Through continuously updated and relevant information from users, social media enables increased participation from online

communities.

3. Sharing of Content, which is a dimension that utilizes social media marketing as a way for individuals to trade, distribute and receive material in situations that allow content to take the form of photos, videos or status updates.

4. Accessibility, namely enabling consumers who have internet access to engage in social media conversations, accessibility emphasizes ease of access and low operating costs in social media marketing.

5. Credibility, namely the company must be able to show its credibility by providing information, helping customers in resolving problems, and responding to customer suggestions or criticism. The term “credibility” refers to sending a clear message to a brand that encourages it to establish credibility through actions or statements that have an emotional connection with the intended audience.

Repurchase Intention

According to Pham et al (2018) Repurchase is described as the client's real activity in purchasing or reusing the item. When customers purchase a particular item, they can make subsequent purchases. This indicates that customers frequently purchase similar services or goods from the same vendor. While repurchase is an actual action, repurchase intention indicates a customer's decision to engage in future activities with the seller. Repurchase intention, as defined by Hellier et al in the journal Christine R (2018), is a cycle in which an individual plans to repurchase comparable services and products based on past experiences. If the value of a product or service is great, customers will be more inclined to buy it again because it makes them feel good and is interesting. Due to emotional desire, consumers often intend to repurchase, which increases repurchase intentions even further.

Repurchase intention according to Ali Hasan (2018) is the intention to make a purchase based on previous history. High repurchase interest reflects a high level of consumer satisfaction with the decision to use or obtain a product. Once a consumer tries a product and determines whether they like it or not after doing so, they decide whether to buy it or not. When customers believe that the goods they use are of high quality and able to satisfy their needs and expectations, liking for the product will develop. Based on this definition, it can be concluded that repurchase intention is a customer's desire to repurchase goods or services in the future because they are happy with the brand previously used. The degree to which consumers are committed to obtaining a good or service influences how likely they are to repurchase. The better opportunities consumers have to make further purchases, the more they want or are interested in a product. The likelihood that consumers will repurchase a used good or service decreases in proportion to the level of interest they have in it. Consumer desires arise from the experience of using a product or service by having a positive experience that makes the product or service the main choice in the future. Apart from that, consumers also provide recommendations for products or services to other people because consumers have had positive experiences, so consumer recommendations to other people do not make other people feel disappointed.

According to Saraswati et al (2021) there are 4 types of repurchase intention indicators, namely:

1. Transactional Interest is an individual's tendency to carry out product

transactions.

2. Referral Interest is where the customer's action recommends goods to other individuals.
3. Preferential Interest is that customers can cause things that have been used as primary decisions.
4. Explorative Interest is the interest of someone who carries out a constant search for product-related information.

Brand Trust

Brand trust is consumers' belief that the company or brand they choose can solve their problems and deserves respect and provides more value. According to Murthy in the journal Anang Firmansyah (2019), brand trust is a business that successfully builds a long-lasting customer brand experience based on the principles of politeness, honesty and integrity. According to Munuera in the journal Ngabiso et al (2021) defines brand trust as when a product or service can meet the needs implemented in the brand based on consumer trust and prioritizing or prioritizing consumer needs, then it has a brand capacity that is trusted by consumers.

Brand trust is a type of buyer's desire to depend on a brand that is in danger because of the assumption that the brand will provide profitable results, according to Lau and Lee in the journal Putu et al (2018). Customer loyalty to a brand is influenced by customer trust in it. According to relationship marketing theory, brand trust will be a major factor in determining initial brand loyalty. According to the description given above, brand trust can be defined as a customer's willingness to believe that a brand will provide favorable outcomes for them, which leads to loyalty and trust in a brand.

According to Delgado in the journal Anang Firmansyah (2019), brand trust indicators are divided into 2 elements, namely:

1. Brand reliability, namely the buyer's certainty that the goods can fulfill what is guaranteed with the view that the brand can solve problems and can also provide satisfaction. As a result, consumers develop trust in a brand when it is able to deliver on its promises and ensure that they will continue to receive the same level of satisfaction. Honesty, convenience, service procedures and services offered to ensure customer satisfaction are all aspects of brand reliability.

2. Brand intention, namely customer assurance that the product can prioritize their needs when unexpected problems with product use develop. Therefore, intentionality refers to the idea that brands will pay attention to what customers need and will not take advantage of their gullibility by offering compensation for problems using the product.

Relationship between Experiential Marketing, Social Media Marketing, Brand Trust and Repurchase Intention

Someone will be willing to make a repeat purchase because the consumer has experienced, felt, and provided experience by purchasing a product that suits their desires and needs as a consumer. Thus, the higher the consumer's experiential marketing, the higher the consumer's repurchase interest in the product they have purchased. Based on research by Yanto (2018) on "The Effect of Experiential Marketing on Repurchase Intention through Experiential Value among Pasa Rame Restaurant

Consumers in Surabaya" and research by Khoirunnisa, et al (2021) on "The Effects of Experiential Marketing and Social Media Marketing on Repurchase Intention with Brand Trust as Variable Mediation for Wearing Klamby Hijab Fashion Products" proves that experiential marketing has a significant effect on repurchase intention.

Many companies use social media as a way to connect, sell, and build connections with their consumers. This communication channel is ideal for exchanging knowledge and ideas. Because social media conveys the brand, customers perceive it as more authentic. The purpose of advertising is to inform customers about the company brand, so this will have an impact on their decision to make a repeat purchase. There are various ways to promote, but Instagram is one of them. Making customers remember a brand or product by using promotional advertising on social media is very important to increase repurchase interest. Based on research by Bawono, et al (2020) on "Analysis of the Effect of Social Media Marketing on Repurchase Intention Through Brand Trust as a Mediating Variable on Instagram Adidas Indonesia in Surabaya" and on research by Khoirunnisa, et al (2021) on "The Effects of Experiential Marketing and Social Media Marketing on Repurchase Intention with Brand Trust as Variable Mediation for Wearing Klamby Hijab Fashion Products" proves that social media marketing has a significant effect on repurchase intention.

Experiential marketing is a marketing effort carried out by a company to focus on creating impressive experiences for consumers. Consumer confidence in the product's ability to fulfill the brand's promises of value and goodwill based on consumer confidence in the brand's ability to prioritize consumer interests is the basis of brand trust. It can be concluded that the relationship between experiential marketing and brand trust is that consumers will be willing to make repeat purchases because these consumers have a sense of trust and feel comfortable with the fulfillment of their desires and needs in purchasing products, because the better the brand experience, the higher the level of consumer trust in the brand. . Based on Oktafia's (2016) research on "Analysis of the Effect of Experiential Marketing on Brand Trust and Customer Loyalty by Mediating Customer Satisfaction (Case Study on Garuda Indonesia Airline Customers in the West Jakarta Region)" and Andriny's (2015) research on "The Effect of Experiential Marketing on Brand Trust and J.CO Donuts & Coffee Customer Loyalty in Pontianak City (Survey of J.CO Donuts & Coffee Customers in Pontianak City)" proves that experiential marketing has a significant effect on brand trust.

One of the keys to establishing a better relationship with a brand is trust, which can also be used to build relationships with future customers. Social media marketing is a new medium for transaction processes when it comes to sharing information and promoting items of business. Using social media as a tool because this marketing tactic has the ability to help businesses achieve their goals, especially through increasing brand trust. Based on research from Irawan et al (2020) on "The Influence of Social Media Marketing Activities on Brand Trust, Brand Equity and Brand Loyalty on the Instagram Social Media Platform" and research by Zulfikar (2017) on "The Effect of Social Media Marketing on Brand Trust on Instagram Followers Dompot Dhuafa Yogyakarta Branch" shows the extraordinary impact of social media marketing on brand trust.

According to Ngabiso et al (2021), brand trust is the capability of a product that is believed by customers when a product or service can meet the demands made on the brand, both based on consumer trust and prioritizing consumer needs. Because it directly influences repurchase intention, building and maintaining brand trust is very

important (Dharmayana & Rahanatha, 2018). Based on research by Juwairiyah (2019) on "The Influence of Brand Image, Brand Trust, and Perceived Value on Repurchase Intention on Lion Air Airplane Tickets (Study on Undergraduate Students at Universitas Brawijaya Malang)" and Dellasari (2020) on "The Influence of Customer Experience and Brand Trust on Repurchase Intention in the Erigo Fashion Brand" has a fairly large impact on brand trust on intention to repurchase.

Consumers believe that with positive feedback from experiential marketing, consumers are willing to make repeat purchases. If someone uses an item repeatedly, then it can be said that the consumer is experienced in using the item and can be judged by trusting the product, so that the consumer has the intention to buy the product repeatedly, and vice versa. This means that the better and increased customer trust that results from experiential marketing, the more likely consumers are to increase their repurchase intentions.

It is recognized that one of the keys to strengthening consumer bonds with a particular brand is trust, which is a factor in long-term bonds with customers. Social media is used as a marketing tool because this approach provides several options to meet company goals, one of which is increasing brand trust. A trusted brand is a brand that succeeds in providing consumers with a memorable brand experience that is built on honesty, politeness and integrity (Murthy in the journal Anang Firmansyah, 2019). Building and maintaining brand trust is very important because orders directly influence a customer's tendency to make more repeat purchases (Dharmayana & Rahanatha, 2018). Based on research by Bawono, et al (2020), it is proven that social media marketing has a significant effect on repurchase intention through brand trust.

Conclusion

Experiential marketing and social media marketing can significantly influence consumers' repurchase intentions through brand trust because marketing through experience and social media is an effective marketing method in helping consumers more easily and efficiently find out consumer beliefs that arise from repeated consumer views that arise. arises from the product purchased, so that if consumers have a good view of a product, it is more likely that consumers will repurchase the product. This article can be used as a reference for other research that has similar variables to this research, namely experiential marketing, social media marketing, repurchase intention, and brand trust. The author hopes that this research can further assess the variables of experiential marketing, social media marketing, and brand trust as factors that can experience repeat purchase interest.

References

- Afifah, K. (2016). *Pengaruh social media marketing Instagram terhadap Tingkat Brand Awareness Roaster and Bear Coffee Lounge & Kitchen*. Universitas Gadjah Mada.
- Andriani, R., & Fatimah, R. (2018). Strategi experiential marketing Sebagai metode Pendekatan Dalam Meningkatkan revisit intention Wisatawan Sabda Alam Garut. *Jurnal Kajian Ilmiah*, 18(3), 206.
<https://doi.org/10.31599/jki.v18i3.287>
- Andriny, Nova. (2015). PENGARUH EXPERIENTIAL MARKETING TERHADAP BRAND TRUST DAN LOYALITAS PELANGGAN J.CO DONUTS & COFFEE DI KOTA PONTIANAK (Survey Pada Pelanggan J.CO Donuts & Coffee di Pontianak). (Skripsi, Program Sarjana Universitas Tanjungpura, Pontianak, Indonesia) Didapat dari <https://jurnal.untan.ac.id/index.php/ejmfe/article/view/12016>
- Christine R. Pardede, S. L. H. V. Joyce Lopian & Merinda Pandowo. (2018). The Influence Of Perceived Value and Trust On Repurchase Intention In Shopee Online Shopping “ *Jurnal EMBA* , Vol.6 no.1 Januari 2018
- Dellasari, Devy. (2020). Pengaruh *Customer Experience* dan *Brand Trust* terhadap *Repurchase Intention* pada *Brand Fashion Erigo*. (Skripsi, Program Sarjana Universitas Telkom, Bandung, Indonesia) Didapat dari https://openlibrary.telkomuniversity.ac.id/pustaka/files/162979/jurnal_eproc/pengaruh-customer-experience-dan-brand-trust-terhadap-repurchase-intention-pada-brand-fashion-erigo.pdf
- Dharmayana, I., & Rahanatha, G. (2018). PENGARUH BRAND EQUITY, BRAND TRUST, BRAND PREFERENCE, DAN KEPUASAN KONSUMEN TERHADAP NIAT MEMBELI KEMBALI. *E-Jurnal Manajemen*, 6(4), 2018-2046.
- Durianto, D., Sugiarto, dan Sitinjak, T. (2017). *Strategi Menaklukan Pasar Melalui Riset Ekuitas & Perilaku Konsumen*. Jakarta: Gramedia.
- Ghozali, L., & Latan, H. (2012). *Partial Least Square : Konsep, Teknik dan Aplikasi SmartPLS 2.0 M3*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- Hair, Joseph F., G. Tomas M. Hult., Christian M. Ringle., and Marko Sarstedt. 2017. *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM)*. 2e Edition USA: Sage.
- Irawan, Alfian Dally & Aswin Dewanto Hadisumarto. (2020). Pengaruh Aktivitas *Social Media Marketing* Terhadap *Brand Trust*, *Brand Equity*, dan *Brand Loyalty*

Pada *Platform Social Media* Instagram. (Skripsi, Program Sarjana Universitas Indonesia, Depok, Indonesia) Didapat dari <https://scholarhub.ui.ac.id/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1045&context=jmui>

Juwairiyah, Syaima. (2019). Pengaruh *Brand Image*, *Brand Trust* Dan *Perceived Price* Terhadap *Repurchase Intention* Pada Tiket Maskapai Penerbangan Lion Air (Studi Pada Mahasiswa/I S1 Universitas Brawijaya Malang). (Skripsi, Program Sarjana Universitas Brawijaya, Malang, Indonesia) Didapat dari <https://repository.ub.ac.id/id/eprint/174626/>

Khoirunnisa, A., & Astini, R. (2021). The effects of experiential marketing and social media marketing on repurchase intention with Brand Trust as variable mediation for wearing KLAMBY hijab fashion products. *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 6(6), 35–41. <https://doi.org/10.24018/ejbmr.2021.6.6.1145>

Mileva, L., & DH, A. F. 2018. *Pengaruh social media marketing terhadap Keputusan Pembelian (survei online pada Mahasiswa Sarjana Jurusan Ilmu administrasi bisnis angkatan 2014/2015 fakultas Ilmu Administrasi Universitas Brawijaya Yang Membeli starbucks menggunakan line)*. *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis*. <http://administrasibisnis.studentjournal.ub.ac.id/index.php/jab/article/view/2421>

Ngabiso, F., Radji, D. L., & Kango, U. (2021). Pengaruh Citra Merek (Brand Image) Dan Kepercayaan Merek (Brand Trust) Terhadap Loyalitas Merek (Brand Loyalty) Pada Produk Air Minum Dalam Kemasan Merek Aqua (Studi Pada Konsumen Amdk Merek Aqua Di Kota Gorontalo). *Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen Dan Bisnis*, 4(1), 1-12.

Pham, Q., Tran, X., Misra, S., Maskeliūnas, R., & Damaševičius, R. (2018). Relationship between convenience, perceived value, and repurchase intention in online shopping in Vietnam. *Sustainability*, 10(2), 156. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10010156>

Priansa, D.J. (2017). *Komunikasi pemasaran terpadu pada era media sosial*, Edisi Pertama. Cv Pustaka Setia.

Ratnasari, N., Susandy, G., & Apriandi, D. W. (2019). THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING AND ONLINCCE CONSUMER BEHAVIOR IN THE CITY OF SUBANG ON THE BRAND STORY OF THE INSTANT MESSENGER LINE APPLICATION . *Diskursus Ilmu Manajemen STIESA (Dimensia)* , 1-10.

Saraswati, K. D., Sanjaya, P. K. A., & Trarintya, M. A. P. (2021). Pengaruh Variasi Produk Dan Store Atmosphere Terhadap Repurchase Intention. *Widya Amarta: Jurnal Manajemen, Kewirausahaan Dan Pariwisata*, 1(2), 431-442.

Sari, N.N., Fauzi, A. and Rini, E.S. (2021) ‘The effect of electronic word of mouth (E-wom) and brand image on repurchase intention moderated by Brand Trust in the

Garuda Indonesia airline', *International Journal of Research and Review*, 8(9), pp. 81–91. doi:10.52403/ijrr.20210912.

Sekaran, U. (2014). *Metodologi Penelitian untuk Bisnis (Research Methods for Business)*. Buku 1 Edisi 4. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.

Skandalis, A., Byrom, J., & Banister, E. (2019). Experiential marketing and the changing nature of extraordinary experiences in post-postmodern consumer culture. *Journal of Business Research*, 97, 43–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2018.12.056>

Tong, T. K. P. B. (2020). Analisa Pengaruh *Social Media Marketing Terhadap Repurchase Intention Melalui Brand Trust* Sebagai Variabel Mediasi Pada Instagram Adidas Indonesia di Surabaya. *Jurnal Strategi Pemasaran*.

Wicaksono, B. E., & Budiarmo, A. (2017) PENGARUH EXPERIENTIAL MARKETING & EMOTIONAL BRANDING TERHADAP REPURCHASE MELALUI BRAND TRUST (Studi Kasus pada Konsumen Garuda Indonesia di Kota Semarang). *Jurnal Ilmu Administrasi Bisnis*, 7(1), 12-23.

Zulfikar, A. R., & Mikhriani, M. (2017). Pengaruh Social Media Marketing Terhadap Brand Trust Pada followers Instagram Dompot Dhuafa cabang Yogyakarta. *Al-Idarah: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Administrasi Islam*, 1(2), 279. <https://doi.org/10.22373/al-idarah.v1i2.1663>